

Special Fast Neutron Shaping filter for the Reference Neutron Field of the LR-0 Reactor

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804184

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new modification of the reference reactor core of the LR-0 reactor is introduced, aiming to create an experimental environment for studying the fast neutron spectrum. The modified spectrum is essential for various nuclear research applications, like Gen IV. research. The process of developing and constructing the fast filter is described. Sets of critical measurements and activation detector measurements were performed. Experiments were conducted using activation detectors to map the neutron flux within the neutron filter. The reaction rates were determined by measuring the activity of the activation detectors using a high-purity germanium (HPGe) detector. From the critical experiments, the -372 pcm calculation to experiment was observed, and this behavior was deeply investigated. Based on the calculated parameters, the main issue is probably connected with the fast fission of the ²³⁸U. The experimental results regarding reaction rate determination showed very good agreement with MCNP code calculations across the whole neutron spectrum energies, with a total discrepancy below 3.4%. The paper demonstrates the suitability of the LR-0 reactor and the modified cavity in the experimental channel for a much harder neutron spectrum for future investigations and testing.

Keywords: LR-0 reactor core, fast neutron spectrum, MCNP, reaction rate measurement, ²³⁸U fission

1. INTRODUCTION

In nuclear research and data validation, there is no such thing as a completely universal neutron field; every single experiment is unique and has its own application and utilization. As we face a nuclear renaissance due to the development of Gen IV and SMR reactors, expanding the experimental capacities of research reactors is essential. This paper presents the step-by-step process of creating a fast neutron insertion filter for the reference neutron field of the LR-0 reactor. This core configuration is particular, as it is constructed in the thermal reactor core with a highly thermalized neutron spectrum. Currently, there are approximately 227 research reactors worldwide, and only about 38 facilities can be classified as fast reactors [1]. The presented modification of the reference neutron field of the LR-0 reactor can significantly expand the capabilities and experimental capacity of this reactor facility.

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2. DESCRIPTION OF EXPERIMENT AND METHODOLOGY

Core modification was prepared at the laboratory of the LR-0 research reactor. This reactor is a zero-power pool-type, light-water-moderated reactor operating at atmospheric pressure and temperature 20 ± 3 °C. As fuel, VVER-1000 fuel assemblies serve with a fission column height of only 125 cm compared to the NPP size. The primary purpose of the reactor is to conduct research and development on VVER-1000 and VVER-440-based reactor cores, as well as to perform criticality, shielding, fission distribution, and reaction rate benchmark experiments. The reactor design allows for building a wide range of core configurations with arbitrary core size, shape, enrichment, and the H_3BO_3 acid content in the moderator. Due to the existence of a larger number of experimental channels, any inserts undergoing examination or neutron field shaping can be placed in the reactor core in arbitrary geometry and amount. Frequently used materials for neutron field shaping include graphite, heavy water, iron blocks, salts, and various liquid materials. The criticality of each core is achieved by adjusting the moderator level in a reactor vessel or by changing the position of the control rod within the fuel assemblies. Thus, the moderator level can play a critical role as a parameter that is often investigated and measured. The continuous nominal power of LR-0 is 1 kW, with thermal neutron flux $\approx 10^9$ cm⁻² s⁻¹ in some specific core positions and configurations. Figure 1 shows the schematic view of the reactor and the schematic of the core arrangement with the developed neutron filter.

Figure 1. The LR-0 reactor schematic general view (left), top photo of the core arrangement (centre), schematic diagram of the core (right)

2.1. Description of the core

The core configuration used as a primary neutron source was a well-known reference neutron field [2] [3] of the LR-0 reactor. This core consists of six fuel assemblies with a nominal enrichment of 3.28, 3.29, and 3.30 wt% of ²³⁵U/U. The fuel is of the VVER-1000 type, with a fuel pin pitch of 1.275 cm and a fuel assembly pitch of 23.6 cm. In the center of the core, a special dry experimental channel was placed, which serves as a fast neutron filter. In the centre of this insertion, the defined volume marked as DET in Figure 2, with a cylindrical shape of 6 cm height and 6 cm diameter, was investigated regarding the shape of the neutron flux. Moreover, the reactor core contains six cylindrical channels, located around one side of the core, which are used to monitor the reactor power. The channels are 4 cm from the fuel assemblies placed in a light water reflector to sufficiently reduce uncertainties based on channel position to the criticality level. This approach has been previously investigated, and the channel placement appears to be appropriate with respect to the sensitivity of the detector and its influence on the critical level.

The central experimental module is sized and shaped to match the VVER-1000 fuel and is constructed from aluminum with a wall thickness of 0.5 cm to minimize the impact on the neutron shape due to absorption. Other construction parts, such as the support socket, are identical to those in fuel assemblies. This experimental module was filled with a developed neutron filter. The primary objective of this newly developed filter was to minimize the thermal neutron flux and maximize the fast neutron flux,

given the available components at the reactor facility. For this reason, only a simple cadmium filter was rejected, as it suppressed the thermal neutron flux without affecting the fast spectrum energies. This new filter was prepared from separate fuel pins, similar to those in fuel assemblies, which surrounded the central cavity in the experimental dry module. The enrichment of the selected pins was 4.4 wt% of ^{235}U to maximize thermal neutron capture. The filter itself was designed as a cylindrical structure with fuel rods arranged in three concentric rows forming one filtering assembly. The rods were placed in a tight geometry, almost touching each other, see Figure 1 and Figure 2. The radius of individual circles of rods forming a neutron filter was also selected with respect to no space created between them when neutrons passed from the driven core to the center of this geometry. The outer radius of the neutron filter is 10 cm, and the inner radius of the filtered area is approximately 7 cm. The filter is formed from 150 fuel pins, exactly 58 rods in the outer circle, 46 in the middle, and 46 rods in the inner circle. As a support plate, it features a drilled aluminum holder at the bottom and a 3D printed spacing grid placed at the top of the geometry to secure the pin position during the experiment and handling. At the bottom of the aluminum holder, a 1 mm thick cadmium plate was placed to minimize the entry of scattered thermal neutrons from the lower part of the core. This was necessary because fuel pins do not shield the area, and the neutrons in this area have a highly thermalized spectrum, as observed in previous work [4]. At the centre of this created geometry, the aluminum activation detector holder, equipped with selected activation detectors, was placed during irradiation.

Figure 2. Photo of the created fast filter (left figure A), side view of the core with marked investigated volume “DET”(middle figure B), photo of real foil holder with special modification (right figure C)

2.2. Mapping of the neutron flux in the neutron filter

A precisely selected set of activation detectors in the form of small foils was chosen for the accurate monitoring of neutron flux in the investigated volume, see Figure 2 (the middle figure B, the investigated volume is marked as “DET”). The activation foils were primarily focused on mapping fast and thermal neutron fluxes. For this purpose, multiple activation detectors made of Fe, Co, In, Ti, Ni, and Na sensitive to different neutron energies were used. Some detectors, for some materials, several dosimeters were placed in the holder. Some of them serve for scaling factor calculation, and some for the neutron flux mapping. Some foils were also covered with an additional Cd filter to estimate the cadmium ratio in this core configuration. The reactions which were investigated were namely $^{58}\text{Fe}(n,\gamma)^{59}\text{Fe}$, $^{59}\text{Co}(n,\gamma)^{60}\text{Co}$ for thermal neutrons mapping, $^{23}\text{Na}(n,\gamma)^{24}\text{Na}$ using Cd for epithermal neutrons and $^{56}\text{Fe}(n,p)^{56}\text{Mn}$, $^{47}\text{Ti}(n,p)^{47}\text{Sc}$, $^{48}\text{Ti}(n,p)^{48}\text{Sc}$, $^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115*}\text{In}$ and $^{58}\text{Ni}(n,p)^{58}\text{Co}$ for precise monitoring of the fast neutron energy range. All activation foils in this preliminary study were placed in the central part of the central volume of the neutron filter, see Figure 2 “DET” marked area.

The activation foil holder consists of four pure aluminum rods arranged in a fixed geometry. Each rod has a diameter of 0.8 mm, and the total height of the holder is 60 cm. In the upper and lower parts, a centering circular plate is located to ensure the radial position of the rods within the filter. Activation

foils were mounted in a special sub-holder, which forms a star-shaped holder. It is placed 24.5 cm from the bottom, which corresponds to half of the critical moderator level, see photo of the real foil holder in Figure 2. The volume investigated in this study encompassed the area around the central rod of the holder. Activation detectors placed on other eccentric rods were used solely for power monitoring and are not part of this evaluation. Irradiation was carried out in a single-step process for 10 hours at a thermal power of approximately 11.3 W to reach sufficient activity of the detectors.

2.2.1. Determination of reaction rate

After irradiation in the core, the activity of the activation detectors was measured using a well-defined HPGe detector, Ortec GEM35, in a vertical configuration [3]. The Net Peak Areas (NPA) are determined using the Genie2K software (Canberra) for the HPGe detector. Efficiency calibration for each energy was calculated using the precise validated HPGe detector model in the MCNP 6.2 code [5] and also validated using multiple sources, see Figure 3. The resonance self-shielding factor was estimated using a fixed source calculation. These calculations were performed with the calculated neutron spectrum obtained from the criticality calculation.

Production rate of the radioisotope in activated material – reaction rate during non-constant irradiation was calculated for each foil, while the capture reactions of the produced radioisotopes are neglected. Coincidence summing effect correction was calculated using the method presented in [6]. More detailed information about this methodology and the entire setup of the HPGe detection system can be found in previous works [3].

Figure 3. HPGe detector efficiency validation with gamma sources in end cap position

2.3. Calculations

All calculations were performed using the MCNP6.2 Monte Carlo code with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 [7] nuclear data library and the corresponding TSL (Thermal Scattering Library). A model of this core configuration was prepared without any significant simplifications, featuring precisely modeled geometry and material composition. All analyses were run in critical calculation mode, with 20,000 active cycles and 200,000 neutrons per cycle. The first 50 inactive cycles were skipped to ensure proper source distribution convergence, which is typically checked after the calculation with a lower number of cycles in testing mode. This critical calculation determined the neutron spectrum in the selected volume, marked as “DET” in Figure 2. The energy group structure of the calculated neutron flux shape consisted of 640 groups in SAND-II format. The size of the scored volume is a 6 cm height cylinder with a 6 cm diameter placed as described above, which corresponds to the volume of the area where the activation detectors were located. Statistical uncertainty of the neutron spectrum at this scored volume situated in the middle of the critical moderator height is less than 0.75% in the energy range from 2×10^{-8} MeV to 6.1 MeV, except for a peak around 7 eV. At higher and lower energies, the uncertainty increases slightly; for instance, at an energy of 12 MeV, the statistical uncertainty is less than 6.5%. This calculated spectrum is used for calculating reaction rates in the activation material, as described above.

The self-shielding factor was determined using separate simplified MCNP simulations performed as fixed-source calculations. The neutron source was modeled as a sphere with a diameter of 8 cm. The activation material was placed at the center of this sphere, which had accurately defined dimensions and shape. The neutron spectrum shape obtained from the criticality calculations was used as a source spectrum for this calculation. In each simulation, 1×10^9 source neutrons were modeled. These self-shielding corrections and other factors were later used to modify experimentally obtained data for possible comparison with the calculated reaction rate.

Finally, the reaction rates of all materials used in the activation foil holder and their comparison with the experiment were computed by multiplying the calculated neutron spectrum by the microscopic cross-sections obtained from the IRDFF-II [8] nuclear data library. This technique determines the reaction rate per one atom in each activation foil.

3. RESULTS

The critical height (H_{cr}) of the moderator level for this core configuration was investigated and measured three times before the activation of the detectors. The experimentally estimated moderator level was the most crucial parameter for the critical calculation and also showed the effect of this filter on the reference case without the neutron filter. In this case, the experimental moderator level was 469 ± 0.32 mm, and the corresponding MCNP calculation result $k_{eff} = 0.99629 \pm 0.00002$, meaning -372 pcm. A strong influence of the developed filter on a critical moderator level can be observed regarding a comparison of a standard reference neutron field on one side, and a strongly thermal core configuration with one graphite module in the experimental channel. The results of these three core configurations, with the same driven core composition except for the experimental channel insertion, are presented along with their experimentally determined parameters in Table I.

Table I. Comparison of the critical height of the moderator level for three modifications of the reference core. Calculation prepared using ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library.

Modification	H_{cr} [mm]	k_{eff} [-] \pm 0.00004	ΔQ [pcm]	ΔQ to reference case [pcm]
Reference core [4]	538.00 ± 0.05	0.99911	-89	0
Graphite core [4]	431.16 ± 0.02	0.99907	-93	-4
Fast filter core	469.00 ± 0.32	0.99629	-372	-283

The agreement between the experiment and calculation is not satisfactory, so this behavior was investigated to identify the inaccuracy in the MCNP model. However, no severe simplifications or mistakes were found in the model. This phenomenon was studied in more detail, based on the calculated results from the MCNP simulation. The neutron filter itself accounts for the most significant discrepancy between the calculation and the experiment for the critical parameter. It was calculated that 4.47% of all fission occurs in the neutron filter, which is a significant proportion. Due to the different shape of the neutron spectrum in the filter's layers, greater attention was paid to this behavior, and key determining parameters were established, which can be seen in Table II.

Table II. Calculated ratios of different fission and capture in the fuel pins placed in the central neutron filter and in the driven core itself.

Row of pins in the filter	^{238}U fiss./ ^{235}U fiss. [%]	^{238}U fiss./ ^{238}U capt. [%]
1. Row	9.3%	18.6%
2. Row	12.0%	23.5%
3. Row	13.1%	24.5%
Average of the filter	11.0%	21.5%
Driven core	5.1%	12.1%

The calculated results are evident that, with decreasing distance from the core center, the share of the fast fission fraction in filter fuel pin rows increases for ^{238}U , and the ratio of ^{238}U fission to capture decreases. The average value for the filter compared to the driven core for both ratios is also very large,

so the higher fraction of neutrons in the filter is attributed to the ^{238}U . This finding, to some extent, explains the origin of the discrepancy in the critical calculation, as the fission of ^{238}U itself is less well understood compared to ^{235}U , and this behavior may be the primary source of uncertainty. On the other hand, this disagreement is unlikely to influence the shape of the neutron spectrum significantly.

For a better understanding of how the newly developed neutron filter affects the shape of the neutron spectrum, a comparison of all the mentioned neutron shape spectra generated using an LR-0 reactor is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Comparison of the calculated neutron spectrum shape in different LR-0 reactor core modifications compared to the new fast core

After the criticality experiment measurement, the activation detector holder was placed at the centre of the neutron filter. After activating the foils, the NPA was determined using the HPGe detector and Genie2K software. Based on measurements and calculations, all reaction rates were normalized to one atom in the activation detector volume. Estimated reaction rates based on measurement were normalized per one neutron using a scaling factor. The scaling factor represents the neutron emission in the whole reactor core during irradiation, it was determined based on these activation detector types namely – Fe, Co, and Ni foils, and was found to be 9.567×10^{11} with a 2.2% uncertainty. The scaling factor is calculated by multiplying the experimentally obtained reaction rate by the self-shielding correction factor and then dividing by the computed reaction rate from the MCNP code calculation.

According to the MCNP code, the average emission per fission was 2.448 neutrons, with an energy released during fission of 180.9034 MeV. Based on these values, the reactor's thermal power during irradiation was calculated to be approximately 11.3 W. It is calculated by dividing the scaling factor by the number of neutrons per one fission multiplied by the energy release during one fission.

In Table III, experimentally determined and calculated reaction rates of the activation foils in the middle of the holder are shown. The uncertainty of the experimental measurement, listed in Table III, was estimated based on the uncertainty of the HPGe detector geometry 1.75%, scaling factor uncertainty 2.2%, foil geometry uncertainty 1%, and measurement uncertainty from 0.1% - 3%. Statistical uncertainty of the calculated reaction rate is lower than 0.3 % for all reactions. Experimental reaction rates were defined as the average value of measured reaction rates from the same detector types. For certain detectors, the averaging of the determined reaction rates was performed not only across two or more specific detectors, but also across different energies evaluated for a single reaction. For instance, the $^{56}\text{Fe}(n,p)^{56}\text{Mn}$ reaction rate was evaluated based on two NPA for energies of 846.6 keV and 1810.9 keV.

Table III. Experimentally determined and calculated reaction rates (RR) for different activation materials and reactions. Experimental reaction rates normalized using a scaling factor, both RR normalized per one neutron.

Reaction	Experimental RR [1/s]	Experimental uncertainty [%]	Calculated RR [1/s]	C/E-1 [%]
$^{56}\text{Fe}(n,p)^{56}\text{Mn}$	7.44E-32	3.1	7.42E-32	-0.3%
$^{56}\text{Fe}(n,p)^{56}\text{Mn} + \text{Cd}$	7.26E-32	3.1	7.24E-32	-0.2%
$^{58}\text{Fe}(n,\gamma)^{59}\text{Fe}$	1.69E-29	3.2	1.74E-29	3.1%
$^{58}\text{Fe}(n,\gamma)^{59}\text{Fe} + \text{Cd}$	8.08E-30	3.4	7.68E-30	-4.9%
$^{59}\text{Co}(n,\gamma)^{60}\text{Co}$	7.21E-28	3.1	7.27E-28	0.9%
$^{47}\text{Ti}(n,p)^{47}\text{Sc}$	1.29E-30	3.0	1.34E-30	3.5%
$^{48}\text{Ti}(n,p)^{48}\text{Sc}$	2.05E-32	3.2	2.05E-32	0.0%
$^{58}\text{Ni}(n,p)^{58}\text{Co}$	7.85E-30	3.0	7.74E-30	-1.5%
$^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115*}\text{In}$	1.39E-29	3.0	1.51E-29	8.9%
$^{23}\text{Na}(n,\gamma)^{24}\text{Na} + \text{Cd}$	1.66E-30	3.1	1.71E-30	2.6%

From the calculations, a nice agreement is observed around all activation detectors, particularly in the fast neutron energy range. A significant reduction is also achieved in the thermal energy range, confirming that the neutron filter effectively reduces the thermal neutron flux, as suggested and calculated. Only the reaction rates for In exceed the specified accuracy, which can be caused by the fact that the In foils were chosen very thin and they were probably placed closer to the larger foils in the holder, so the self-shielding effect of other foils can play a non-negligible role.

The cadmium ratio for selected reactions can be determined as a possible indicator of the amount of thermal neutrons in the whole neutron spectrum. In our case, the cadmium ratio was determined for the $^{58}\text{Fe}(n,\gamma)^{59}\text{Fe}$ reaction. This parameter is calculated as the ratio of reaction rates between a bare detector and a detector covered with a cadmium filter. A comparison of different cadmium ratios for various LR-0 cores configurations can be seen in Table IV. For this comparison, a large graphite core [9] was also included due to its highest share of thermal neutrons among all LR-0 created cores.

Table IV. Experimentally determined cadmium ratio for selected reaction $^{58}\text{Fe}(n,\gamma)^{59}\text{Fe}$ in three different reactor core configurations at the LR-0 reactor.

Core configuration	Cadmium ratio [-]
Reference core	6.492
Large graphite core [9]	11.272
Fast filter core	2.092

It can be clearly seen that the primary goal of cutting off the thermal neutrons from the reference case is achieved with sufficient efficiency. The second goal of developing this neutron filter was to increase the fast neutron flux in the experimental channel, which is also evident. For a proper non-graphical comparison of all three LR-0 reference core modifications with the new fast filter, the numerical share of the neutron amount was quantified in Table V. When comparing the reference core with a fast filter core, an increase of approximately 26.5% in the total flux was observed in the energy range from 10 keV to 20 MeV.

Table V. Calculated share of neutrons in selected energy ranges for three different LR-0 cores, normalised by total flux.

Energy range [MeV]	Reference core	Fast filter core	Single graphite core
$1 \cdot 10^{-10} - 6.25 \cdot 10^{-7}$	19%	6%	26%
$6.25 \cdot 10^{-7} - 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	12%	10%	13%
$1 \cdot 10^{-4} - 1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	13%	13%	15%
$1 \cdot 10^{-2} - 2$	37%	49%	35%
2 - 20	18%	22%	10%

4. CONCLUSIONS

A fast neutron filter was successfully constructed and tested as part of this work to achieve a faster neutron spectrum at the reference neutron core of the LR-0 reactor. The effect of the core's criticality regarding the new neutron filter insertion was investigated, and a disagreement of approximately -283 pcm was observed. This discrepancy is attributed to the fast fission of ^{238}U in the neutron filter, which may play a significant role in the critical parameter, which could also be linked to the poor description of the ^{238}U cross section. In the centre of the filter, a preliminary study using activation detectors was conducted to determine the reaction rates and map the neutron flux. It can be said that all activation detectors achieve great agreement between their calculations and experiments. Considering the results, the newly developed neutron filter achieved the set goals of suppressing the thermal neutron flux and maximizing the fast neutron spectrum flux within the defined volume. This study demonstrates that the design can be utilized for future measurements, focusing on higher neutron energies. The agreement for the neutron spectrum and reaction rates is satisfactory, and this core configuration can serve as a more challenging neutron field compared to the reference core of the LR-0 research reactor.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The presented results were obtained using the CICRR infrastructure, which is financially supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports - project LM2023041, and within the project VB0200063 „Methods of remote monitoring of ionising radiation levels with an energy resolution of sources“ with financial support from the state budget through the Ministry of the Interior of the Czech Republic in Program Security research of the Czech Republic 2021-2026.

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